

The minimis aid in agriculture in Spain

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Abstract

L'une des caractéristiques du secteur agricole en Espagne est l'énorme dispersion de l'information affectant ce secteur, fragmentation due à l'étendue et à la variété des registres agricoles. À l'énorme liste des registres agricoles administratifs, il faut ajouter ceux relatifs aux informations sur la réception des aides et des subventions au secteur agricole. En ce qui concerne la perception des aides agricoles, il faut également tenir compte des aides dites de minimis, qui sont incluses dans le système national de publicité des subventions et des aides publiques. Dans ce contexte, les aides de minimis sont réglementées, également au profit du secteur agricole. Ce document explique l'origine et le fonctionnement de la base de données des aides de minimis ainsi que ses objectifs.

Eines der Merkmale des Agrarsektors in Spanien ist die enorme Streuung der diesen Sektor betreffenden Informationen, eine Fragmentierung, die auf den Umfang und die Vielfalt der Agrarregister zurückzuführen ist. Zu der umfangreichen Liste der landwirtschaftlichen Verwaltungsregister kommen noch diejenigen hinzu, die sich auf Informationen über den Erhalt von Beihilfen und Subventionen für den Agrarsektor beziehen. Im Zusammenhang mit den agrarischen Beihilfen müssen auch die so genannten De-minimis-Beihilfen berücksichtigt werden, die in das nationale System der Bekanntmachung von Subventionen und öffentlichen Beihilfen einbezogen sind. In diesem Zusammenhang werden diese De-minimis-Beihilfen auch zugunsten des Agrarsektors geregelt. Der Beitrag erläutert Entstehung und Funktionsweise der Datenbank für De-minimis-Beihilfen sowie deren Ziele.

1. Particularities of the agricultural sector in Spain

In 2022, the National Institute of Statistics presented the new Agrarian Census in Spain with reference to the year 2020, in the compilation of which the collaboration of the Ministry of Agriculture, Fisheries and Food (MAPA), through the Spanish Agricultural Guarantee Fund (FEGA) and the Sub-directorate General for Analysis has been fundamental. This Census gives extensive statistical information on the configuration of agricultural holdings in Spain. In addition to the usual statistical information, the new Agrarian Census, which is compiled every ten years, offers a novel interactive monograph with maps that allow comparisons to be made and allow the user to configure a selection of data *à la carte*. Likewise, for the first time, it incorporates segmented information at the level of agricultural districts, this is in addition to the usual information by autonomous communities and provinces. The National Institute of Statistics plans to update most of the statistical content in the Agrarian Census on an annual basis to guarantee their validity and continuing usefulness.

The recently presented Agrarian Census data shows a reduction in the number of agricultural holdings in Spain of 7.6% with respect to the previous edition, although the utilised agricultural area has grown by 0.7% and exceeds 23.9 million hectares. This translates into an increase in the average size of farms, which stands at 26.37 hectares, 7.4% more than in 2009.

Castilla y León recorded the highest average size per holding (63.02 hectares) and the Canary Islands the smallest (4.81 hectares). The number of livestock grew by 6.5% compared to the last census. The growth was more intense in the case of pigs, with 21.8%. The farm labour force decreased by 7.7% in 2020 compared to the previous census. In 2020, the area under organic farming accounted for 7.8% of the total utilised agricultural area.

One of the most significant data is the increase in the role of women in farming in recent years, which is reflected in a 22% increase in the number of female farm managers. We should consider the contribution of our Law 35/2011 on shared ownership of farms to this. The law states that in rural family farms, there are many women who share agricultural tasks with men, taking on a large part of the work and contributing both goods and labour, but in most cases only the man is the owner of the farm, which makes it difficult for women's participation in the rights and obligations derived from the management of the farm to be properly valued.¹

In Spain, there are obviously no legal limitations to women's access to property or agricultural property, but it is true that a specific status for the spouse collaborating in the farm has been requested. This law attempted to provide a certain response to these demands. To this end, the present law regulates the shared ownership of farms. The Law offers a new legal figure/figuration of a voluntary nature. Its objective is to go beyond a regulation of administrative effects, since it is a question of promoting positive action that manages to give visibility to women. The figuration that is created – shared ownership – is outlined as an economic unit, without legal personality, and susceptible to taxation for tax purposes, which constitutes a married couple or unmarried couple, for the joint management of the farm, differentiating between the ownership of the farm and the ownership of the assets and their rights, whose civil legal regime is not affected in any case. This Law grants these jointly owned farms priority status, in accordance with Law 19/1995, of 4th July 1995, on the modernisation of agricultural holdings, so that they will enjoy the advantage of having priority in obtaining benefits, aid and other promotion measures promoted by the Public Administrations, provided that one of them is a professional farmer and the unit income from work obtained from the farm does not exceed 50 percent of the maximum established in the corresponding legislation for priority farms.

The Law also regulates another mechanism for the recognition of the economic rights of women who carry out tasks on the farm. Thus, those who, having participated effectively and regularly, do not receive any payment or consideration for the work carried out and have not formed a shared ownership with their spouse or common-law partner, will be entitled to financial compensation in the event of the transfer of the farm and/or the termination of the marriage or common-law partnership.

In addition to the above, there is the possibility of access to joint administration of the farm, but without creating the legal figuration of shared ownership, through the constitution of a limited liability company as provided for in article 5.2 of Royal Decree-Law 13/2010, of 3rd December, on tax, labour, and liberalisation measures to promote investment and job creation, whose statutes shall be in accordance with the standard statutes approved by the Minister of Justice.

Not many farms have made use of the modalities of this law, or have taken on the shared ownership, but it has been partly an incentive to give visibility to the activity of women in agriculture. At this point it could be said, in any case, that this law has run its course and we should be thinking about new

¹ See GAMAZO, J.C., “Evolución de la actividad agropecuaria en el s.XXI de acuerdo con los datos del censo agrario”, nº 258, 2022, p. 18.

formulas that would serve to develop and advance the incorporation of women into the agricultural business.

2. The specific aids scheme in agriculture

The aids scheme is essential for the maintenance of agricultural assets and the development of agricultural holdings, but Spain does not have a very transparent basis for knowing its scope and impact. As regards aids and subsidies to the agricultural sector in Spain, mention should be made of direct aid payments, the basic payment, the supplement to the green payment, direct and specific aid to young farmers including the simplified scheme for small farmers, and payments associated with protein and legume crops, oilseeds, quality pulses and beet. Regarding aid for young farmers for the next CAP, it is foreseen that for 5 years those who join as young farmers will be granted an additional and more important premium when it comes to the incorporation of young women. There are also structural aids: for the improvement of farms, for the purchase of machinery or for agricultural insurance. There are also agri-environmental aids or contractual aids and rural development aids, which are partly those of the modernisation law for priority farms and partly those attributed to the local action groups that administer projects of the old LEADER initiative.

In any case, support for the sector has taken the form of numerous types of aid. Action has been taken on competition or concentration processes, on the structural stability of agricultural markets, on investments in agricultural structures, on a pricing policy, with tariffs on imports and export refunds, by promoting the use of new generation technologies, both in production and in distribution and marketing. It also specifically promotes collaborative and cooperative² approaches, already considered in an incipient way in Regulation 1305/2013³; these could include models of reciprocal collaborative contracts between agricultural companies, as a means to expand and project themselves more easily into more competitive and international markets, through the strengthening of the negotiating

² Not only by encouraging associations, but also by favouring institutions that can be included in the collaborative economy movement, in this commitment to greater social responsibility, less waste of resources and more responsible consumption, motivating changes in social behaviour. However, instruments have yet to be regulated in a more specific way in the agricultural sector which, by making the obligations and rights of the parties clear, would encourage their greater use, given their favourable repercussions on costs. In any case, the idea of partnership is emphasised in the future CAP from various perspectives, with the Leader programme and the activities of the local action groups taking the same objectives into account. For a general overview of this new form of economy, see BULCHAND, J.-MELIAN, S., *La revolución de la economía colaborativa*, LID ed., 2018; LES-SING, L., *Remix. Making Art and Commerce Thrive in the Hybrid Economy*, Bloomsbury Academic, 2008; FELSON, M-SPAETH, J.L., "Community Structure in Collaborative Consumption. A Routine Activity Approach", *The American Behavioral Scientist*, vol. 21, no. 4, 1978, 614 ff; SMORTO, G., "Verso la disciplina giuridica della sharing economy", *Merc. Conc. Reg.*, 2015, pp. 245 et seq. Also see MALAURIE VIGNAL, M., "L'économie collaborative ou les métamorphoses du capitalisme?", *Contrats Concurrence Consommation*, May, 2016, repère 5; BERNHEIM-DESVAUX, S., "La consommation collaborative ou participative", *Contrats Concurrence Consommation*, 2015, étude 2; CLÉMENT-FONTAINE, M., "La genèse de l'économie collaborative: le concept de communauté", *Dalloz IP/IT*, 2017, pp. 140 et seq. The Cost of Non-Europe in the Sharing Economy, Economic, Social and Legal Challenges and Opportunities, European Parliamentary Research Service, January 2016; MUÑIZ ESPADA, E., *Relaciones contractuales de cooperación en el medio agrario y rural*, Aranzadi, Navarra, 2020.

³ Cf. clauses 4 & 29.

autonomy of the parties⁴. Priority is also given to contractual mechanisms in all their different aspects⁵, and more specifically, protection is provided through the protection of contractual relations based on force and the value of information, with the legislator intervening with a control over the content of the contract, as another defence against the consequences of the liberalisation of agricultural markets⁶. In this sense, the new models of reciprocal collaboration contracts between companies⁷ represent a great opportunity for large companies and, in any case, represent development initiatives for rural territories.

3. The *minimis* aids in agriculture in Spanish law. Its end goal

In relation to the receipt of aid for the agricultural sector, it is also necessary to consider the so-called *the minimis* aid, included in the national system of advertising subsidies and public aid.

In this regard, it should be remembered that according to Article 107 TFEU, aid granted by States or through state funds that distorts or threatens to distort competition will be incompatible with the internal market, but aid intended to promote the economic development of regions where the standard of living is abnormally low or considering their structural, economic, and social situation will be compatible. To this end, the Commission shall keep under constant review, together with the Member States, the aid schemes existing in those States. It shall propose to the latter any appropriate measures required by the progressive development or by the functioning of the internal market. If the Commission finds that aid granted by a state or through state resources is not compatible with the internal

⁴ Cf. modalities that are included in the European principles contained in the *Small Business Act*, which guide EU and national policies.

⁵ Thus: "producer organisations, interprofessional organisations, cooperatives and associations."

⁶ Cf. , NATOLI, R., *L'abuso di dipendenza economica. The Contract and the Market*. Napoli, 2004; MACARIO, F., "Abuso di autonomia negoziale e disciplina dei contratti fra imprese: verso una nuova clausula generale?", *Riv. dir. civ.*, 2005, pp. 663ff.; DELLI PRISCOLI, L., "Abuso di dipendenza economica e contratti di distribuzione", *Riv. dir. impr.* 2003, pp. 548ff.; RUSSO, L., "I nuovi contratti agrari", *Riv. dir. agrario*, 2013, pp. 41 ff.

⁷ cf. , SPOTO, G., *I contratti di rete tra imprese*, Torino, 2017, "in order to overcome the economic crisis and to be more competitive in the era of globalisation and economic exchanges, small and medium-sized enterprises have sought collaboration policies for the achievement of common goals. These are instruments that do not conflict with the rules of competition and do not contravene the prohibitions of state support, but which are created to develop a programme open to all subjects with the same interests. The author pays particular attention to their application in the agrarian field, where the phenomenon has, unsurprisingly, found a wide expansion. In fact, the discipline of collaboration contracts has further evolved in the various forms of integration between companies in the agricultural sector. The agricultural enterprise has the possibility of associating "in rete" to cultivate the land and share the products obtained on the basis of percentages fixed in the contract, making it possible to compensate for any production shortfalls of each of the participants. The participants in the relationship could thus decide to use the result of such shared production on their own farm or to put the production on the market. The possibility of organising one's own labour resources and sharing one's own tools to put them at the common service makes it possible to overcome the limits linked to local productions and short supply chains in such a way as to expand distribution. It is clear that the opportunities for companies linked in the network will certainly be more expansive than if they chose to act individually. This will also make it possible to achieve rural development objectives, because in this way the entrepreneur will be able to overcome the economic disadvantages associated with fragmentation, and obtain benefits that will also be reflected in environmental policies. Collaboration between different subjects thus becomes an alternative means to the classic business model."

market under Article 107, or that such aid is being misused, it shall decide that the state concerned shall abolish or alter it within a period of time to be determined by the Commission, Art. 108 TFEU.

In this context, so-called *the minimis* aid is regulated, also for the benefit of the agricultural sector. In particular, the Commission has adopted a series of regulations laying down rules on *the minimis* aid granted in this sector in Commission Regulation EU 1408/2013, as amended by Regulation 2019/316. In the light of the experience gained in the application of the above-mentioned regulation, and given the different ways in which *the minimis* aid is used in the Member States, it was appropriate to adapt some of the conditions laid down therein: including, the maximum amount of aid that can be granted to a single enterprise over a three-year period – which it was considered should be increased, and the national ceiling on annual production.

In view of the increasing need to use *the minimis* aid and given that the ceilings proved to be excessively restrictive, albeit within the derogation they entail, it became necessary to amend EU Regulation 1408/2013 before its expiry date, i.e. 31 December 2020. For reasons of procedural economy and to ensure continuity and legal certainty, the period of application of EU Regulation 1408/2013 should be extended until 31 December 2027.

As an increased need for the use of *the minimis* aid was identified in some Member States, an additional increase of both the maximum amount of aid for a single undertaking to 25,000 euros and the national ceiling to 1.5 % of annual production was authorised, subject to additional conditions necessary to ensure the proper functioning of the internal market.

The precondition for making use of the individual ceiling and the higher national ceiling should be the application of a sectoral ceiling preventing Member States from granting, during any period of three fiscal years, more than 50 % of the total cumulated amount of *the minimis* aid for measures benefiting only a specific product sector. That sectoral cap should ensure that any measure falling within the scope of Regulation EU 1408/2013 does not have any effect on trade between Member States and does not distort or threaten to distort competition.

In Spain such *the minimis* aid in agriculture has been used to support measures for very specific purposes, for example, to help prevent or eradicate animal diseases as soon as an outbreak occurs, or to compensate farmers for damage caused by animals that are not protected by EU or national legislation⁸, or to favour the farming activities of women in rural areas, or to support environmental programmes. They have also been used on occasions, as has been acknowledged, in crisis situations, in sectors such as the dairy or pig sectors, or to compensate for certain damage to plantations due to adverse weather conditions which were not covered by agricultural insurance. They have also been granted to the "green harvest"⁹ programme.

In Castilla y León, as one of the autonomous communities in Spain with the greatest tradition and agricultural activity, *the minimis* aid has been granted, especially, to farmers and stockbreeders associations, to agricultural boards, to cooperative societies and also to shared ownership farms which were developed from the 2011 law to give visibility to the work of women in agricultural activity¹⁰.

⁸ Agrodigital.com.

⁹ "Vendimia en verde", which is part of the *Plan de Apoyo al Sector Vitivinícola*, cf. Royal Decree 283/2021 on green harvesting.

¹⁰ *Ley 35/2011, de 4 de octubre*, on shared ownership of agricultural holdings.

These are *the minimis* aids granted for agricultural activities, livestock farming and post-harvest preparation, and also in the field of livestock production.

4. The national database for the publicity of public subsidies and aids

In Spain, a national database for the publicity of subsidies and public aid has been created, which includes a specific section for so-called *the minimis* aid.¹¹ In this database, only those public administration bodies that have registered applications or awards of subsidies in accordance with the general criteria are eligible for selection. Thus, the different ministries of the Spanish State appear as grantors, such as the Ministry of Agriculture, and other bodies, local authorities and autonomous communities. In turn, some Autonomous Communities, or autonomous communities, have their own public database of subsidy and aid, including the *minimis* aid. This database publishes: the beneficiary to whom the aid has been granted, the activity carried out by the beneficiary, the type of aid, whether it is a grant, loan, guarantee, financial contribution or tax advantage, and the purpose for which the aid is intended. This will facilitate the monitoring of aid granted in order to simplify and improve the delivery and control of so-called *the minimis* aid.

This database includes the tenders which are publicly registered in the National System of Publicity of Subsidies and Public Aids. By clicking on the title (in Spanish or in a co-official language) or on the BDNS code, you can access the data and documents of the application - the type of awarding body, the title of the application and the date also appear.

As for the convener, only those public administration bodies that have registered tenders or grant awards as of 01/01/2016 (01/01/2014 in the case of the state public sector) are selectable.

The alert subscription service allows you to create a standard alert associated with an email account, modify the alert query, or delete it. When subscribing, or modifying the subscription criteria, the system sends a message confirming the alert criteria chosen by the interested party or the administered party. Whenever there is a match between your subscription criteria and the publication of a tender, you will receive an e-mail message similar to this: "*the National System for the Publicity of Public Subsidies and Grants informs you that a tender has been registered in accordance with the criteria associated with the given e-mail address*".

Also published in this database are the beneficiaries who have obtained grants in all the years in which this publicity register has been in operation.

Infringements and sanctions are also published in this database.

5. Verification and monitoring of the *minimis* aid in agriculture

In order to verify and monitor the level of *the minimis* aid, it has already been established at Community level that a central register in each Member State is necessary. It is optional for Member States

¹¹ <https://www.pap.hacienda.gob.es/bdnstrans/GE/es/concesiones/minimis>

to use a central national register to check that neither the individual ceiling for *the minimis* aid nor the national ceiling is exceeded. However, the use of a central register is mandatory in those Member States which opt for the higher individual ceiling and national cap, as the sectoral cap, which is a precondition for that option, requires an even stricter control of the aid granted. It should therefore be mandatory for such Member States to establish and maintain a central register of all *the minimis* aid granted, in order to be able to verify that neither the individual ceiling nor the national or sectoral cap is exceeded. "Where a Member States grants aid pursuant to Article 3(3a), it shall maintain a central register of *the minimis* aid containing complete information on all *the minimis* aid granted by any authority within that Member State. Paragraph 1 shall cease to apply from the moment the register covers a period of three fiscal years", Art. 6.2 Regulation 2019/316.

In Spain, the Ministry of Agriculture, the Regional Ministries of Agriculture and even Town Councils and Provincial Councils can grant this type of *the minimis* subsidy to help farms in difficulty in their territorial area without requesting authorisation from Brussels, albeit based on their own budgetary resources. Thus, agricultural associations and organisations have welcomed the fact that the scope for the State to support measures in the event of sectoral difficulties or crises has been extended in this way.

The national database for the advertising of public subsidies and aids contains a specific section for the so-called *the minimis* aid¹². In this database, only those public administration bodies that have registered tenders for applications or awards of subsidies in accordance with the general criteria are eligible for selection. Thus, the different ministries of the Spanish State appear as grantors, such as the Ministry of Agriculture, and other bodies, such as local authorities and autonomous communities. In turn, the Autonomous Communities have their own database for publicising subsidies and aid, including *the minimis* aid. This database publishes: the beneficiary to whom the aid has been granted, the activity carried out by the beneficiary, the type of aid, whether it is a grant, loan, guarantee, financial contribution or tax advantage, and the purpose for which the aid is intended.

This will facilitate the monitoring of aid granted to simplify and improve the delivery and control of the so-called *the minimis* aid, as this database includes the public tenders registered in the National System of Publicity of Subsidies and Public Aid and publishes the beneficiaries who have obtained the aid, also from previous years. Infringements and penalties are also published in the same database.

This national database of subsidies and financial aid thus unifies the information on national public aid and public subsidies, which brings together those granted by the State itself and those granted by the public administrations or other public bodies of the Autonomous Communities or local entities. However, the characteristic feature of the agricultural sector in Spain is the fragmentation of its information, with an enormous dispersion of the existence of agricultural administrative bases and registers, which makes the control and management of this sector difficult, with very negative consequences for this economic sector in particular and for the country's economy in general. This is being addressed in the recently presented draft law establishing and regulating the information system for agricultural and livestock holdings and agricultural production.

¹² <https://www.pap.hacienda.gob.es/bdnstrans/GE/es/concesiones/minimis>

It is acknowledged that the agricultural public administrations have at their disposal a large amount of information and data provided by farmers and stockbreeders themselves, and by companies supplying goods and equipment to the agricultural sector; furthermore, as stated, agricultural producers are obliged to manage a series of registers containing information on animal movements, veterinary treatments, agricultural plots and the application of phytosanitary products. As mentioned above, all this information is contained in a set of databases and administrative registers distributed between the Ministry of Agriculture and the Autonomous Communities, according to their own scope. The aim now is to provide greater coherence and integrity through an interconnected information system, to simplify the work that farmers and stockbreeders must carry out, both when applying for subsidies and when it comes to justifying compliance with obligations, sometimes in order to obtain such subsidies. The aim of this change is to simplify the task of farmers and stockbreeders and to improve digitalisation processes, avoiding duplication of information and facilitating access to it for farmers and stockbreeders themselves.

The aim is that the information generated will allow progress in the design, implementation and management of agricultural policies with a direct impact on the CAP, simplifying the presentation by farmers of the single annual application in which the different lines of CAP¹³ aid are included. The administration will thus have the necessary elements to prepare the draft application for each farmer, with the data needed to manage his dossier. It is also recognised that it will enable the planning and evaluation of the implementation of the CAP strategic plan and the 'Farm to Fork' strategy, including the monitoring of indicators and legislative measures therein. It will also be the way to obtain higher quality agricultural statistics, which will facilitate a better design of sectoral actions, to achieve economic production, also in relation to the environment and the conservation of biodiversity.

In a positive way, this legislative project aims to establish a unified information system for the agricultural sector, but this same idea of unification and a single register for the entrepreneur is represented in our legal system by the Commercial Register, which is characterised above all by the production of a series of effects of protection and legal certainty that cannot be guaranteed by administrative registers. Thus, given the legal configuration and regulation of the Commercial Register, no administrative register exceeds the guarantees and protective effects provided by the Commercial Register itself.

In contrast to the function of the administrative agricultural registers, it is the entry in the Commercial Register that enables the achievement of numerous purposes: advertising, informative, evidential, statistical, programmatic, market protection and freedom of competition, rationalising the organisation of companies operating on the market and for the market without distinction, as well as

¹³ Art. 3.1. "To enable efficient planning, implementation and management of the CAP 2023/2027 and to contribute to the assessment of compliance with the CAP Strategic Plan 2023/2027 following the system of indicators of the new delivery model, which form the Performance Framework according to Chapter I of Title VII of Regulation (EU) 2021/2115 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 2 December 2021, laying down rules concerning support for the strategic plans to be drawn up by the Member States under the common agricultural policy (CAP strategic plans), financed by the European Agricultural Guarantee Fund (EAGF) and the European Agricultural Fund for Rural Development (EAFRD), and repealing Regulations (EU) No 1305/2013 and (EU) No 1307/2013".

highlighting the relationship between the real destination link and the requirement for an appropriate advertising regime.